

NEXUS BETWEEN NON-PERFORMING LOANS AND BANK PROFITABILITY: A CASE FROM PAKISTAN CONVENTIONAL BANKING SECTOR

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ABSTRACT

The banking sector plays a critical role in any economy by facilitating financial intermediation, credit allocation, and economic growth. In Recent years the global banking system has been changed and every business, businessman, investors, corporations' entrepreneurs and personnel affected by positive changes in worldwide banking system. This study investigates the relationship between capital adequacy, bank size, non-performing loans (NPLs), and bank profitability within Pakistan's conventional banking sector. It further examines the role of corporate governance in influencing bank performance. Given the critical role banks play in economic stability, effective governance and credit risk management are essential to mitigate financial distress and institutional failure. Using a quantitative approach, the study analyzes secondary data from the annual reports and financial statements of selected commercial banks in Pakistan over a ten-year period (2014–2023). A multiple regression model was employed to test the proposed relationships. The findings reveal that both capital adequacy and bank size are significantly associated with the level of non-performing loans. Additionally, corporate governance demonstrates a notable, positive influence on bank profitability, while a positive relationship is observed between NPLs and profitability. The results offer important insights for policymakers and banking professionals in enhancing governance frameworks and risk management strategies to ensure long-term financial stability and improved performance in the banking sector.

Keywords: Non-performing loans; Bank profitability; Capital adequacy; Bank size; Corporate governance.

INTRODUCTION

In the global economy, the banking industry is significant. By making loans to both domestic and international businesses, the banking industry supports economic expansion (Nguyen, 2024). On the other hand, excessive lending may expose this practice to a wide range of credit risk. In order to control non-performing loans (NPLs) and deteriorating NPLs, banks prioritize bank credit risk management. The primary source of issues with the banking sector and financial crises is non-performing loans (NPLs) (Us, 2018). The

COVID-19 pandemic has recently resulted in a significant global economic slump. Due to loan defaults, an increase in non-performing loans is unavoidable. According to Do et al. (2020), since 2008, non-performing loans (NPLs) have grown and became unanticipated. An economy's performance might be severely hampered by an increase in non-performing loans. Due to credit market interaction brought on by NPLs, a nation's economy becomes financially insecure. Furthermore, the socioeconomic sector is more

affected by NPLs than by inflation. Even if the nation's economy is expanding and all social indices are showing improvement, non-performing loans are hurting the economy severely (Akhter, 2023). On the other hand, sluggish economic activity, a weak monetary and fiscal policy, and a higher rate of inflation raise the bank's exposure to credit risk, which in turn threatens the financial stability of the bank and the economy as a whole (Anita et al., 2022).

The primary cause of credit risk is the rise of non-performing loans (NPLs), which have a direct impact on financial institutions, particularly banks. For example, the 1997 and 2008 Asian financial crises were caused by the banking system's unstable non-performing loans (NPLs) (Anita et al., 2022). The NPLs ratio is a sign of a financial crisis since it reduces bank loan expansion, which jeopardizes the stability of the national economy (Ivanović, 2016). Increased non-performing loans also put more pressure on interest income, reduce investment prospects, and have a significant impact on the liquidity crisis, which raises the risk of national bankruptcy (Anita et al., 2022). Furthermore, commercial banks are impacted by large non-performing loans (NPLs), which increases their exposure to credit risk and endangers the nation's financial institutions and economy. High NPLs lead even the strongest economies to become vulnerable (Naili & Lahrichi, 2022).

The primary causes of non-performing loans (NPLs) that are directly linked to bank collapse are subpar loan appraisals and insufficient loan disbursement monitoring and oversight. Ineffective oversight and management on the part of the bank, ineffective lender recourse, ineffective legal infrastructure, and ineffective debt collection tactics are the main causes of bank non-performing loans (NPLs). Banks' overall credit quality is lowered by high NPL levels (Adhikary, 2006). According to Kroszner (2002), banks are reluctant to extend more credit when non-performing loans (NPLs) are high due to a lack of capital, which would further depress the economy's output sector. The influence of risk management on non-performing loans (NPLs) and the profitability of Pakistan's banking industry is examined by Haneef et al. (2012). They find that a lack of risk management results in high NPLs, which jeopardizes banks' profitability. Banks may steer clear of non-

performing loans (NPLs) by implementing strategies recommended by their national central banks. Isik and Bolat (2016) demonstrate that among the bank-specific variables, liquidity, profitability, reliability of credit, diversity, economic expansion, and the recent financial crisis are significant indicators of the non-performing loan (NPL) rate in the Turkish banking sector. This is based on a sample of 20 deposit banks in Turkey for the 2006–2012 period. They come to the conclusion that although greater capital and loan loss provisions result in more problem loans, greater profitability and income diversification decrease problem loans. When non-performing loans (NPLs) are high, banks seek to improve asset quality rather than extend credit and increase loan loss provisions, which lowers bank earnings and money available for future lending.

An essential component of Pakistan's economy is the banking industry. The basic functions of the banking sector are to support economic expansion by offering financial services to both consumers and corporations in terms of accepting deposits from customers and lending to those who need it and handling the cash inflow & outflow etc. The banking industry has undergone considerable changes recently, including the use of new technologies (Pratiwi et al., 2023). According to the State Bank of Pakistan (Arby, 2004), a whole number of banks (57) are operating of which, 26 banks are operated commercially, 22 banks are operated in Islamic terms, 8 banks are specialized and 1 bank is working as an investment bank.

A fundamental tenet of bank operations and strategic direction, corporate governance has an important impact on the performance of banks (Osei-Baidoo et al., 2023). Many factors have been shown to have a significant role in influencing the governance structure of banks, which in turn impacts the financial performance of these institutions. These factors fall under the broad category of corporate governance. These dimensions cover a wide range of elements such as board size, independence, gender diversity, audit committee size, CEO leadership qualities, CEO gender (men and women), ownership structure, and management. All of these together influence the governance architecture of banks that operate all working in the complex financial sector.

Various determinants that influence on bank profitability has been investigated in the different studies such as NPFs and bank profitability (Karim et al., 2022; Nguyen, 2024), Analysis NPL and LDR towards profitability (Saleh & Winarso, 2021), Impact of Operating Costs, Capital Adequacy Ratio, Loan-to-Deposit Ratio, Non-Performing Loans and Operational Revenue on Profitability (Syafrizal et al., 2023). Nguyen (2024) suggest assessing the influence of corporate governance on bank profitability with the determinants of non-performing loans. The objective of this study is to examine the influence of bank size and Capital Adequacy on non-performing loans, while also examine the influence of non-performing loans and corporate governance influence on bank profitability.

In order to carry out the study, 10 commercial banks in Pakistan are examined during a ten-year period, from 2014 to 2023. The study especially looks into the following research questions:

- Are NPLs impacted by firm-specific characteristics such as commercial banks' capital adequacy and bank size?
- Do NPLs and corporate governance affect the profitability of commercial banks in Pakistan?

Comprehending the efficacy of corporate governance methodologies in Pakistani Islamic banks is of paramount importance to many stakeholders. Firstly, this study can clarify how different governance configurations like the makeup of the board and the traits of the CEO— affect these organization's financial outcomes. This information can help regulators and policymakers create frameworks that support robust governance procedures that are specific to the requirements of Islamic banking. Regulators may promote better financial stability and public trust in the Islamic banking industry, which will ultimately aid in the area's growth and progress, by enhancing governance.

This study is used to examine how different corporate governance frameworks, such as the makeup of the board and the qualities of the CEO, affect the performance of Islamic banks in Pakistan. With the use of this information, legislators and banks operating in Pakistan may establish solid governance frameworks that will eventually support the sector's expansion and financial stability.

2. Literature Review

Recent research has increasingly focused on understanding why some organizations consistently outperform others in terms of profitability. One such strategy for enhancing organizational performance is the stakeholder theory, which emphasizes fulfilling stakeholder interests to gain a competitive edge. This approach suggests that organizations must meet the needs of stakeholders, whose contributions to the organization add value and ultimately increase profitability (Freeman, 1984).

Corporate governance is a crucial aspect of organizational management that is gaining increasing attention from scholars and business professionals. Scholars and experts have thoroughly examined the ways in which various corporate governance frameworks impact financial outcomes, including metrics such as return on equity (ROE) and return on assets (ROA). This literature study aims to provide a comprehensive synthesis existing literature in order to clarify the intricate relationship between these important performance metrics and corporate governance practices.

2.1 Agency Theory

Agency theory is one of the most well-known theoretical frameworks used in the extensive body of research that has investigated the connection between corporate governance and bank performance. When discussing the interaction between management and shareholders, agency theory focuses on the reasons that each party might behave in their own best interests rather than in line with the objectives of the principal.

Many studies on "bank performance" and "corporate governance" have already been conducted using different components of these variables. These factors are explained by a variety of theories, agency theory being one of them. Agency theory explains why each party can sometimes behave in their own interests rather than the interests of the principle by describing the link between an agent and a principle. The idea holds that ownership and control of a business should remain separate because giving one person these responsibilities would put the board's independence in jeopardy, lead to a conflict of interest, and hinder the operation of the company (Krause et al., 2014).

It is also clarified by the theory that corporate ownership and management control should remain distinct. The separation of ownership and control becomes blurred when a single individual possesses both ownership and management control (Filatotchev, 2012). This overlap can result in potential conflicts of interest and has the potential to compromise the board's independence and impede its capacity to effectively oversee management. This can also result in a decrease in a company's performance when left unchecked, as the board may become incapable of guaranteeing that management decisions are following shareholder objectives (Krause et al., 2014).

2.2 Nature of Relationships in Banking

Agency Theory primarily concerns the association between shareholder (stakeholders) and agents (managers). In the banking sector, this relationship is crucial because managers (agents) make decisions that directly affect the bank's financial outcomes, which, in turn, impact shareholders (principals). Agency Theory helps to clarify how different governance systems, including board structure and quality, can mitigate conflicts and align the interests of both parties. These dynamics are essential in the banking industry, where decision-making processes are highly influential in determining organizational success or failure. By utilizing Agency Theory, we can better understand the potential conflicts that arise between managers and owners and explore how effective governance structures can reduce these conflicts.

2.3 Corporate Governance

The statement emphasizes how important corporate governance is to organizational management and success, which has generated significant scholarly interest in the topic. The intricacy and wide range of effects that corporate governance has inside organizations are highlighted (Mallin, 2007) and also highlights its multifarious character. To comprehend how governance practices and procedures affect company behavior and results, scholars have studied them in great detail. The focus on corporate governance is a reflection of the understanding that it is a key aspect in defining the performance of an organization and the generation of shareholder value. The significance

of sound governance processes and institutions in negotiating the intricacies of contemporary corporate contexts is highlighted by this research focus. In general, the reference highlights the value of corporate governance research in improving management techniques and organizational performance.

The preliminary research conducted on corporate governance can positively impact bank performance and use dimensions (Board Size, Board Independence, Audit Committee size, Ownership Structure, Board Gender Diversity of Board, and Management Ownership) and ROA, ROE, and EPS (Herdjiono & Sari, 2017; Owen & Temesvary, 2018; Sarkar & Sarkar, 2018).

Corporate governance assumes an essential part in forming the construction and the board of associations, especially in monetary organizations like banks. A framework guarantees responsibility, transparency, and decency inside an organization, shielding the interests of investors and different partners. The meaning of corporate governance in the financial area couldn't possibly be more significant, as banks are intrinsically perplexing and work under severe guidelines because of their vital job in the economy (De Haan & Vlahu, 2016). The hypothetical groundwork of corporate governance is fundamentally founded on the organization hypothesis, which features the irreconcilable situation between investors (directors) and administrators (specialists). Governance components are important to moderate organization costs, guaranteeing that administrators act to the greatest advantage of investors. Different systems, similar to the partner hypothesis, expand the idea of governance by stressing the more extensive obligation of enterprises toward all partners, including representatives, clients, and the local area (Freeman, 1984).

The board of directors size is the most essential dimension of corporate governance that significantly affect the performance of a bank (Detthamrong et al., 2017) because it includes the major responsibilities to development of Mission & Vision statement, maintaining effective control and risk management and making policies & strategies for an organization.

The board member ensures that every resource, fund, and assets are utilized to obtain optimal output without their concern. Agency and

Resource Dependence theory both explain that a huge number of BS can positively influence the firm performance and also include significant improvements in accounting measures that ultimately improve the market measure of bank performance because board members have diverse knowledge, experience, skills, and certificates (Arora & Sharma, 2016; Farag et al., 2018). Whereas, Stewardship theory concludes that a small board size the firm is more effective than a large board because, a large board causes delays in decision-making, lack of communication, and more free riders. According to stewardship theory, companies benefit more from smaller boards than from bigger ones. According to this viewpoint, bigger boards may result in inefficiencies including poor communication, a delay in decision-making, and a higher chance of free-riding among board members. (Sarkar & Sarkar, 2018; Wallgren & Andersson, 2018) Give this claim empirical evidence to back it up. Stewardship theory underscores the need for streamlined and agile decision-making procedures in corporate governance frameworks by supporting reduced board sizes. This viewpoint is consistent with the idea that smaller boards have a greater capacity to cultivate a shared sense of accountability and responsibility among their members, which improves organizational performance and the efficacy of governance.

According to a preliminary study of (Sarkar & Sarkar, 2018), both men and women have different characteristics and traits in their personalities, educational qualifications, abilities, experience, communication skills, and timely and effective decision-making abilities. According to Agency theory, diversity on board is good for the firm in terms of better monitoring of management that leads to enhanced concert of the firm (Athar et al., 2023). Board gender diversity can recover corporate governance and lead to more diverse and effective decision-making making which ultimately enhances the firm's performance (Brogi & Lagasio, 2022).

As per critical mass theory, including women on board is beneficial for the firm because, it decreases the agency cost and makes decisions timely & efficiently ultimately increasing the bank's performance (Athar et al., 2023) and (Owen & Temesvary, 2018). According to (Green & Homroy, 2018) performance of a firm is

directly impacted by women's participation on boards, which is a more accurate measure of board gender diversity. Females on the board of directors are more likely than male directors on board to monitor more closely, which could enhance the firm performance with subpar governance procedures (Adams & Ferreira, 2009).

Whereas, some studies argue that women on board lead to a decrease the firm performance because, as per tokenism theory women have three fears: solitude, assimilation, and not being acknowledged for their contributions so, they can't give their full participation.

As per previous studies, agency theory suggests that BI is positively influencing organizational performance (Boyd, 1995). Because these boards are regarded as independent, the division of parts may help them carry out their supervision responsibilities more successfully (Finkelstein & Mooney, 2003). According to (Brogi & Lagasio, 2022), BI shows a positive relation to bank performance that leads to an increase in performance and a decrease in risk. According to a preliminary study by (Osei-Baidoo et al., 2023), results show that board of director independence can positively affect performance and ultimately enhance the performance of the bank.

Another study by (Liang et al., 2013) shows that BI has a positive relationship to bank performance. According to (Bansal et al., 2023), board of director independence can positively influence the bank's performance. As per (Zahoor et al., 2023), BI can weaken the relationship between international CSR and post-entry performance which means that it shows a negative relationship between them. As per (Al-Faryan & Alokla, 2023), results show that BI of Saudi insurance firms has a positive relation with the financial performance of the firm. The study marks explain that, board independence is positively affecting the bank's performance (Maxfield et al., 2018).

2.4 Bank size and NPLs

Bank size is determined by taking the natural logarithm of the bank's total assets ratio, which shows the capital strength of the bank for that year (Durguti, 2020). NPLs decrease with the size of the bank (HU et al., 2004). This conclusion is in line with those of Yulianti et al. (2018) and Panta (2018), who discovered a negative

correlation between bank size and non-performing loans (NPLs). This suggests that larger banks are able to minimize their risk by allowing for more diversification.

Thus, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H₁: Bank size has a negative impact on non-performing loans.

2.5 Capital Adequacy and NPLs

The Basel Accord established the capital adequacy ratio (CAR), which is reviewed by bank supervisory agencies to manage risk and shield banks from going bankrupt (ElBannan, 2017). According to Madugu et al. (2020), banks with a strong provision policy and a higher CAR have fewer problem loans. Numerous studies, including those by Siddique et al. (2022) and Ghenimi et al. (2017), have demonstrated a significant correlation between CAR and bank risk. However, Louzis et al. (2012) found no correlation between CAR and banks' risk, suggesting that the tiny Greek bank market discourages banks from taking careless risks and being short-termist due to reputational factors. They contend that in order for regulatory bodies to exercise appropriate supervision over banks' risky loan portfolios, they attempt to adhere to a supervisory policy. Delis et al. (2012) also found that capital regulation may have a positive or negative impact on the bank's risk, depending on the bank's characteristics, other regulations, and factors like the macroeconomic environment.

Thus, the following hypothesis is proposed;

H₂: Capital Adequacy of a bank has positive influence on non-performing loans.

2.6 Corporate Governance and Bank Profitability

The statement emphasizes how important corporate governance is to organizational management and success, which has generated significant scholarly interest in the topic. The intricacy and wide range of effects that corporate governance has inside organizations are

highlighted (Mallin, 2007) and also highlights its multifarious character. To comprehend how governance practices and procedures affect company behavior and results, scholars have studied them in great detail. The focus on corporate governance reflects the understanding that it is a key aspect in defining the performance of an organization and the generation of shareholder value. The significance of sound governance processes and institutions in negotiating the intricacies of contemporary corporate contexts is highlighted by this research focus. In general, the reference highlights the value of corporate governance research in improving management techniques and organizational performance (Herdjiono & Sari, 2017; Owen & Temesvary, 2018; Sarkar & Sarkar, 2018). So, the following hypothesis proposed;

H₃: Corporate governance has a significant positive relationship with bank profitability.

2.7 Non-performing Loans and Bank Profitability

There are differing views among scholars about the connection between bank profitability and non-performing loans. Some of them demonstrate a favorable influence, while the majority show a negative one. According to Qehaja-Keka et al. (2023) non-performing loans (NPLs) have a detrimental impact on bank profit because they enable banks to inflate loan losses due to distortions brought about by insufficient restrictions. Using a risk-averse approach in an attempt to increase profit has a detrimental impact on bank managers (Kanapiyanova et al., 2023). When banks manage their credit risk more effectively, they may make more money. When NPLs rise, asset quality might decline and banks may become less profitable.

Thus, the following hypothesis is proposed;

H₄: NPLs have a significant relationship with bank profitability.

Figure 2.1 Conceptual Model

3. Methodology

This study will utilize a quantitative research design and analyze secondary data gathered from financial statements and corporate governance reports of commercial banks in Pakistan. The researcher will use panel data for regression analysis of data of a secondary nature. The commercial banks are randomly selected. This implies that bank-level data collection and analysis will take place. Given that bank size, capital adequacy, non-performing loans and corporate governance elements are all measurable at the organizational level.

In this study, a cross-sectional research approach will be used. All variables' data will be gathered during a predetermined period previous 10 years

from 2015 to 2024. The investigation will be conducted with little influence from researchers because secondary sources have made the data easily accessible. To evaluate the research objectives and hypotheses previously described, this study will employ a quantitative, non-contrived, cross-sectional design with secondary data from commercial banks in Pakistan.

The profitability of Pakistan's banks, capital adequacy, bank size, non-performing loans and corporate governance will all be examined in this study using secondary data. The information about variables will be gathered from annual reports of the chosen commercial banks in Pakistan.

Following are the measurements of the variables:

Table 3.1 Measurements

Variable(s)	Measurements	Reference
Bank Profitability ROA	Net income/total asset	(Boachie, 2023)
Corporate Governance	number of independent commissioners divided by the number of commissioners	(Boachie, 2023)
Nonperforming loans	Nonperforming loan / Total loan	(Nguyen, 2024)
Capital Adequacy Ratio	Total Capital Ratio (Capital Adequacy Ratio)	(Akhter, 2023)
Bank Size	The natural log of total assets	(Boachie, 2023)

3.1 Econometric Model

The study uses the direct effect, which has a direct relationship between variables and may be constructed using a baseline regression model. There is a direct relationship between Bank size, Capital Adequacy Ratio, Non performing loans, Corporate governance, and bank profitability with return on assets measure of the bank performance, this factor also affects ROA that may be affected by these factors directly with earnings per share another measure of bank performance.

The econometric model can be expressed as:

$$NPLS_i = \alpha + \beta_1 BS_i + e_i \quad (1)$$

$$NPLS_i = \alpha + \beta_1 CPR_i + e_i \quad (2)$$

$$NPLS_i = \alpha + \beta_1 BS_i + \beta_2 CPR_i + e_i \quad (3)$$

$$BP_i = \alpha + \beta_1 NPLS_i + e_i \quad (4)$$

$$BP_i = \alpha + \beta_1 CG_i + e_i \quad (5)$$

$$BP_i = \alpha + \beta_1 NPLS_i + \beta_2 CG_i + e_i \quad (6)$$

4. Results

This chapter focuses on the quantitative data analysis and outcomes, which were obtained using the STATA. The findings contain all of the test results used to ensure normality, linearity, and model specification. The results demonstrate the relevance of the relationship based on the

premise. These correlations are examined for numerous concerns to solve, including multicollinearity. However, the results offer an overview of how data-driven relationship analysis takes place, as well as the importance of the link

between variables. This section examines the impact of all analytical data. Nonetheless, the findings provide comprehensive insight into the concept.

4.1 Descriptive statistics

Table 4.1 Summary Statistics

Variable	Observations	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
Board Size	100	7.143	0.0987	6.9	7.3
Capital Adequacy Ratio	100	16.25	3.1881	10	22.5
Non-performing loans	100	22.075	4.6407	14.2	29.85
Corporate governance	100	1.8072	0.8168	0.63	4.38
Bank profitability (ROA)	100	3.35	0.7124	2	4.8

The descriptive statistics of the variables studied provide valuable insights into the characteristics of the banking sector under analysis. The log of bank size (bslog) exhibits a mean of 7.143 with a small standard deviation of 0.0987, indicating a tight distribution of bank sizes, which suggests that the sizes of the banks in this sample are relatively consistent. In contrast, the Capital Adequacy Ratio (car) shows a mean of 16.25% with a standard deviation of 3.1881, revealing some variability among banks regarding their capital buffers, as evidenced by the range from 10% to 22.5%.

The average level of Non-Performing Loans (npls) stands at 22.075 billion PKR, with a standard deviation of 4.6407, highlighting a moderate presence of bad loans across the banks, while the values range from 14.2 billion PKR to 29.85

billion PKR, reflecting significant differences in loan performance. Corporate Governance (cg), measured by the ratio of independent commissioners, has a mean value of 1.8072 and a standard deviation of 0.8168, indicating variability in governance practices among banks; the values range from 0.63 to 4.38, suggesting that while some banks have robust governance structures, others significantly lag behind. Finally, the Return on Assets (roa) averages at 3.35% with a relatively low standard deviation of 0.7124, indicating that the banks tend to maintain similar profitability levels. Overall, these statistics indicate a banking sector with a mix of consistency in bank size and profitability, contrasted by variability in capital adequacy and governance practices, which may impact the overall stability and performance of the sector.

4.2 Linearity Test

4.2.1 Residual plot

Figure 4.1 Residual plot for linearity of variables
 In the residual plot Figure 4.1, which shows no discernible patterns or curves, the zero line is encircled by a random distribution of residuals. This suggests that the linearity assumption of the regression model is probably met. Additionally, the residuals appear to have a very uniform distribution throughout the fitted value range, indicating the validity of the homoscedasticity assumption (constant variance of errors). Conclusion: Based on the graphic, it seems that the linear model fits the data well.

4.3 Normality Test

The normality of the data is verified using the Skewness and Kurtosis tests. A P-value less than 0.05 indicates that the data are not regularly distributed. If the P-value exceeds 0.05, the data is deemed to be regularly distributed. According to tab. 4.2, the results show that the data is regularly distributed. Because the values of skewness (0.3410) and kurtosis (0.4785) are less than one. Also, the P-value is larger than 0.05.

Table 4.2 Skewness and kurtosis tests

Constructs	F	Pr (Skewness)	Pr (Kurtosis)	adj chi2(2)	Prob>chi2
E	100	0.3410	0.4785	1.25	0.5350

One of the assumptions of the regression model is to test the normality of the residuals. The residuals, or mistakes, of the regression line have a nearly normal distribution. The residuals themselves must be regularly distributed, even if

the hypothesis test needs normality to be valid. In actuality, a normal residual is necessary for the t-test to be valid. The data are regularly distributed, based on the Kernel density estimation.

Figure 4.2 Kernel density estimate test

4.4 Multicollinearity

Table 4.3 of the multicollinearity test results show that there are no significant difficulties with multicollinearity among the variables in your model. VIF values indicate how much the variance of each variable's coefficient is exaggerated due to multicollinearity with other variables. In general, VIF values below 10 are considered acceptable, suggesting that there is no serious multicollinearity. Table 4.2 shows that

Npls has the greatest VIF at 4.60, followed by CAR at 3.43, BS at 3.37, and ROA at 1.98. The model's mean VIF of 3.26 suggests that multicollinearity is not a major worry, given all VIF values are much lower than the critical threshold of 5. This is further corroborated by the 1/VIF data, which reveal that CG has the greatest value (0.506), suggesting minimum collinearity. Overall, the test results show that the regression model's exogenous variables are not likely to cause multicollinearity.

Table 4.3 Multicollinearity Test

Variable	VIF	1/VIF
BS	3.37	0.296
CAR	3.46	0.289
Npls	4.60	0.217
CG	1.98	0.506
ROA	2.89	0.346
Mean VIF	3.26	

VIF = 1; no multicollinearity, VIF<5; moderate multicollinearity, VIF≥5; high multicollinearity

4.5 Correlations

Table 4.4 Correlation Statistics

Variable	Car	Npl	cg	roa	bslog
Car	1				
Npl	0.2146	1			
Cg	-0.7589	0.1113	1		
Roa	0.3669	0.7309	-0.0471	1	
Bslog	0.0457	0.4133	0.4873	0.5134	1

The correlation matrix illustrates the relationships among the variables of interest in the banking sector study. The Capital Adequacy Ratio (car) exhibits a significant negative correlation with Corporate Governance (cg) of -0.7589, suggesting that higher levels of corporate governance are associated with lower capital adequacy. This inverse relationship may imply that banks with more independent oversight tend to maintain a more conservative capital structure. Additionally, the correlation between Non-Performing Loans (npl) and Return on Assets (roa) is notably positive at 0.7309, indicating that banks with higher levels of non-performing loans tend to have lower profitability, as measured by ROA. This reinforces the idea that asset quality is a critical factor influencing bank profitability.

Other correlations include a moderate positive correlation of 0.3669 between car and roa, suggesting that banks with higher capital adequacy ratios may also exhibit better profitability, albeit the relationship is not very strong. The correlation between bslog (log of bank size) and npl shows a positive value of 0.4133, indicating that larger banks might experience a higher level of non-performing loans, although this requires further investigation to understand the underlying causes.

Overall, the correlation analysis reveals important relationships between governance, asset quality, and profitability in the banking sector, highlighting areas for further research and potential implications for banking practices and regulations.

4.6 Regression Analysis of Non-Performing Loan

Source	SS	df	MS	Number of obs	=	100
Model	446.032541	2	223.01627	F(2, 97)	=	12.83
Residual	1686.02997	97	17.3817523	Prob > F	=	0.0000
Total	2132.06251	99	21.535985	R-squared	=	0.2092
				Adj R-squared	=	0.1929
				Root MSE	=	4.1691

npl	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]
bslog	19.00388	4.2483	4.47	0.000	10.57219 27.43558
car	.2855099	.1315674	2.17	0.032	.024385 .5466349
_cons	-118.3093	30.32601	-3.90	0.000	-178.498 -58.12054

The results from the regression analysis provide significant insights into the factors influencing non-performing loans (NPL) in the banking sector. The overall model explains approximately 20.92% of the variance in non-performing loans, as indicated by the R-squared value of 0.2092, with an adjusted R-squared of 0.1929, which accounts for the number of predictors in the model. The F-statistic of 12.83 and a Prob > F value of 0.0000 confirm that the model is statistically significant, indicating that at least one of the predictors is significantly associated with NPL.

In terms of individual predictors, the coefficient for the log of bank size (bslog) is 19.00388 with a standard error of 4.2483, yielding a t-value of 4.47 and a p-value of 0.000. This indicates that for each one-unit increase in the log of bank size, non-performing loans are expected to increase by approximately 19.00 units, with high statistical significance ($p < 0.001$), suggesting a strong positive relationship between bank size and non-performing loans.

The Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR) has a coefficient of 0.2855099 with a standard error of 0.1315674, resulting in a t-value of 2.17 and a p-value of 0.032. This implies that a one-unit increase in the capital adequacy ratio is associated with an increase of about 0.29 units in non-performing loans, which is statistically significant at the 5% level. The constant term ($_cons$) is -118.3093 with a standard error of 30.32601, indicating the expected value of non-performing loans when all predictors are zero. The negative coefficient reflects the baseline level of non-performing loans in the absence of the influences of the independent variables.

Overall, the analysis highlights the importance of both bank size and capital adequacy in understanding the dynamics of non-performing loans in the banking sector, suggesting that larger banks and those with higher capital adequacy may experience higher levels of non-performing loans, a finding that merits further exploration in policy and risk management contexts.

4.7 Regression Analysis of bank profitability

Source	SS	df	MS	Number of obs	=	100
Model	27.6871374	2	13.8435687	F(2, 97)	=	59.51
Residual	22.5628629	97	.232606834	Prob > F	=	0.0000
				R-squared	=	0.5510
				Adj R-squared	=	0.5417
Total	50.2500003	99	.507575761	Root MSE	=	.48229

roa	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]
cg	-.1134504	.0597136	-1.90	0.060	-.2319654 .0050645
npl	.1144387	.0105104	10.89	0.000	.0935784 .135299
$_cons$	1.028793	.2494555	4.12	0.000	.533693 1.523893

The regression analysis investigates the relationship between Return on Assets (ROA) and two key independent variables: Corporate Governance (CG) and Non-Performing Loans (NPL). The model demonstrates statistical significance, evidenced by an F-statistic of 59.51 and a p-value of 0.0000, indicating that the independent variables together explain approximately 55.10% of the variability in ROA, as reflected in the R-squared value. The coefficient for corporate governance is -0.1135, suggesting that improvements in CG are associated with a decrease in ROA by approximately 0.114 units. However, this

relationship is marginally significant with a p-value of 0.060, indicating that while it approaches significance at the 10% level, it does not achieve conventional significance at the 5% level.

In contrast, the analysis reveals a significant positive relationship between non-performing loans and ROA, with a coefficient of 0.1144, indicating that for every one-unit increase in NPL, ROA increases by about 0.114 units. This relationship is statistically significant at the 1% level ($p = 0.000$), challenging conventional expectations that higher non-performing loans signal financial distress. Instead, this finding may

suggest effective management practices or a willingness to take on greater risk within the banking sector. The constant term indicates that the expected ROA is approximately 1.03 in the absence of both independent variables. Overall, the results highlight the complex interplay between corporate governance and non-performing loans in determining ROA, suggesting avenues for further research to understand the underlying factors influencing these relationships.

5. Conclusion and Implications

These findings aimed to investigate the impact of bank size and CAR on non-performing loans, as well as the influence of corporate governance and non-performing loans on bank profitability. The evaluation included a few quantifiable approaches, such as regression analysis and multicollinearity tests, to examine both direct and indirect consequences. This section discusses a literature review based on the current writing project. The area where the results align with or differ from previous assessments receives special emphasis. The findings of the regression analysis show that Non-performing loans and bank profitability are considerably impacted by a number of independent variables. Financial performance is positively impacted by non-performing loans, according to the positive and significant coefficient of non-performing loans. This result is consistent with earlier research that shows how various viewpoints and decision-making can improve business performance.

The research serves to substantiate the widely recognized notion that the performance of banks is positively impacted by robust CG. Non-performing loans and corporate governance were identified as critical factors that enhance financial performance. The quality of decision-making is generally enhanced by a diverse and larger board, as a result of the diverse range of perspectives, experiences, and expertise that are available (Adams & Ferreira, 2009). Additionally, the board's independence was discovered to be positively correlated with improved performance metrics, which is in line with prior research that emphasizes the significance of independent directors in enhancing accountability and diminishing managerial discretion. (da Silva et al., 2017). Previous research has frequently concentrated on the direct impact of governance

mechanisms on performance, but it has paid less attention of non-performing loans on bank profitability. This study addresses that lacuna by illustrating that CG mechanisms have a more significant positive effect on performance.

There are some limitations of this study that can be addressed in the future. First, the present study obtained data from (2014-2023) the limited conventional banking sectors. As a result, the timelines are not perfect. Hence, if future research can obtain current data, it can examine recent situation. Second, a similar study can also be extended to different conventional and non-conventional banking sectors of Pakistan.

References

- Adams, R. B., & Ferreira, D. (2009). Women in the boardroom and their impact on governance and performance. *Journal of financial economics*, 94(2), 291-309.
- Adhikary, B. K. (2006). Nonperforming loans in the banking sector of Bangladesh: realities and challenges. *Bangladesh Institute of Bank Management*, 4(26), 75-95.
- Akhter, N. (2023). Determinants of commercial bank's non-performing loans in Bangladesh: An empirical evidence. *Cogent Economics & Finance*, 11(1), 2194128.
- Al-Faryan, M. A. S., & Alokla, J. (2023). Do publicly listed insurance firms in Saudi Arabia have strong corporate governance? *Economies*, 11(1), 21.
- Anita, S. S., Tasnova, N., & Nawar, N. (2022). Are non-performing loans sensitive to macroeconomic determinants? an empirical evidence from banking sector of SAARC countries. *Future Business Journal*, 8(1), 7.
- Arby, M. F. (2004). State Bank of Pakistan: Evolution, functions and organization.
- Arora, A., & Sharma, C. (2016). Corporate governance and firm performance in developing countries: evidence from India. *Corporate governance*, 16(2), 420-436.

- Athar, M., Chughtai, S., & Rashid, A. (2023). Corporate governance and bank performance: evidence from banking sector of Pakistan. *Corporate Governance: The International Journal of Business in Society*, 23(6), 1339-1360.
- Bansal, A., Samontaray, D. P., Aljalalma, A. K. A., & Khadim, M. D. T. (2023). Does the Board Influence the Bank's Performance? An Islamic & Commercial Banking Experience. *International Journal of Professional Business Review*, 8(3), e01080-e01080.
- Boachie, C. (2023). Corporate governance and financial performance of banks in Ghana: the moderating role of ownership structure. *International Journal of Emerging Markets*, 18(3), 607-632.
- Boyd, B. K. (1995). CEO duality and firm performance: A contingency model. *Strategic management journal*, 16(4), 301-312.
- Broggi, M., & Lagasio, V. (2022). Better safe than sorry. Bank corporate governance, risk-taking, and performance. *Finance Research Letters*, 44, 102039.
- da Silva, J. P., Bonfim, M. P., Noriller, R. M., & Berner, C. V. (2017). Mechanisms of corporate governance and performance: analysis of public companies listed in BM&FBovespa. *Race: revista de administração, contabilidade e economia*, 16(3), 1161-1184.
- De Haan, J., & Vlahu, R. (2016). Corporate governance of banks: A survey. *Journal of Economic Surveys*, 30(2), 228-277.
- Delis, M. D., Tran, K. C., & Tsionas, E. G. (2012). Quantifying and explaining parameter heterogeneity in the capital regulation-bank risk nexus. *Journal of Financial Stability*, 8(2), 57-68.
- Detthamrong, U., Chancharat, N., & Vithessonthi, C. (2017). Corporate governance, capital structure and firm performance: Evidence from Thailand. *Research in International Business and Finance*, 42, 689-709.
- Do, H., Ngo, T., & Phung, Q. (2020). The effect of non-performing loans on profitability of commercial banks: Case of Vietnam. *Accounting*, 6(3), 373-386.
- Durguti, E. A. (2020). Challenges of banking profitability in eurozone countries: Analysis of specific and macroeconomic factors. *Nашe gospodarstvo/Our economy*, 66(4), 1-10.
- ElBannan, M. A. (2017). The financial crisis, Basel accords and bank regulations: An overview. *International Journal of Accounting and Financial Reporting*, 7(2), 225-275.
- Farag, H., Mallin, C., & Ow-Yong, K. (2018). Corporate governance in Islamic banks: New insights for dual board structure and agency relationships. *Journal of International Financial Markets, Institutions and Money*, 54, 59-77.
- Filatotchev, I. (2012). 14 Corporate governance issues in competitive strategy research. *Handbook of research on competitive strategy*, 300.
- Finkelstein, S., & Mooney, A. C. (2003). Not the usual suspects: How to use board process to make boards better. *Academy of Management Perspectives*, 17(2), 101-113.
- Ghenimi, A., Chaibi, H., & Omri, M. A. B. (2017). The effects of liquidity risk and credit risk on bank stability: Evidence from the MENA region. *Borsa Istanbul Review*, 17(4), 238-248.
- Green, C. P., & Homroy, S. (2018). Female directors, board committees and firm performance. *European Economic Review*, 102, 19-38.
- Haneef, S., Riaz, T., Ramzan, M., Rana, M. A., Ishaq, H. M., & Karim, Y. (2012). Impact of risk management on non-performing loans and profitability of banking sector of Pakistan. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 3(7), 307-315.
- Herdjiono, I., & Sari, I. M. (2017). The effect of corporate governance on the performance of a company. Some empirical findings from Indonesia. *Central European Management Journal*, 25(1), 33-52.
- HU, J. L., Li, Y., & CHIU, Y. H. (2004). Ownership and nonperforming loans: Evidence from Taiwan's banks. *The Developing Economies*, 42(3), 405-420.

- Isik, O., & Bolat, S. (2016). Determinants of non-performing loans of deposit banks in Turkey. *Journal of Business Economics and Finance*, 5(4), 341-350.
- Ivanović, M. (2016). Determinants of credit growth: The case of Montenegro. *Journal of Central Banking Theory and Practice*, 5(2), 101-118.
- Kanapiyanova, K., Faizulayev, A., Ruzanov, R., Ejdy, J., Kulumbetova, D., & Elbadri, M. (2023). Does social and governmental responsibility matter for financial stability and bank profitability? Evidence from commercial and Islamic banks. *Journal of Islamic Accounting and Business Research*, 14(3), 451-472.
- Karim, R., Roshid, M. M., Shamme, F. B., & Hasan, M. M. (2022). Non-performing loans and bank profitability: Evidence from Bangladesh. *International Journal of Finance & Banking Studies (2147-4486)*, 11(4), 95-102.
- Krause, R., Semadeni, M., & Cannella Jr, A. A. (2014). CEO duality: A review and research agenda. *Journal of Management*, 40(1), 256-286.
- Kroszner, R. (2002). Non-Performing Loans. *Monetary Policy and Deflation: The Industrial Country Experience, Economic and Social Research Institute Cabinet Office, Government of Japan*.
- Liang, Q., Xu, P., & Jiraporn, P. (2013). Board characteristics and Chinese bank performance. *Journal of banking & finance*, 37(8), 2953-2968.
- Louzis, D. P., Vouldis, A. T., & Metaxas, V. L. (2012). Macroeconomic and bank-specific determinants of non-performing loans in Greece: A comparative study of mortgage, business and consumer loan portfolios. *Journal of Banking & Finance*, 36(4), 1012-1027.
- Madugu, A. H., Ibrahim, M., & Amoah, J. O. (2020). Differential effects of credit risk and capital adequacy ratio on profitability of the domestic banking sector in Ghana. *Transnational Corporations Review*, 12(1), 37-52.
- Mallin, C. (2007). *Corporate Governance*: Oxford University Press. In: USA.
- Maxfield, S., Wang, L., & Magaldi de Sousa, M. (2018). The effectiveness of bank governance reforms in the wake of the financial crisis: A stakeholder approach. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 150, 485-503.
- Naili, M., & Lahrichi, Y. (2022). The determinants of banks' credit risk: Review of the literature and future research agenda. *International Journal of Finance & Economics*, 27(1), 334-360.
- Nguyen, P. D. (2024). Non-performing loans and bank profitability: evidence from Vietnam. *Macroeconomics and Finance in Emerging Market Economies*, 1-21.
- Osei-Baidoo, D., Opoku, O. A., & Okudzeto, H. (2023). Effect Of Corporate Governance On Performance Of Listed Banks. *American Journal of Economic and Management Business (AJEMB)*, 2(4), 131-143.
- Owen, A. L., & Temesvary, J. (2018). The performance effects of gender diversity on bank boards. *Journal of Banking & Finance*, 90, 50-63.
- Panta, B. (2018). Non-performing loans and bank profitability: Study of joint venture banks in Nepal. *International Journal of Sciences: Basic and Applied Research (IJSBAR)*, (2018) Volume, 42, 151-116.
- Pratiwi, A. R., Peryoga, D., & Mazaya, G. H. (2023). The Effect of Income and Funding Diversification on Bank Performance and Risk in Indonesia. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Economics and Finance*, 5(1), 60-66.
- Qehaja-Keka, V., Ahmeti, S., & Aliu, M. (2023). Bank profitability determinants: Evidence from Kosovo and Albania. *Journal of Liberty and International Affairs*, 9(2), 297-311.
- Saleh, D. S., & Winarso, E. (2021). Analysis of non-performing loans (NPL) and loan to deposit ratio (LDR) towards profitability. *International Journal of Multicultural and Multireligious Understanding*, 8(1), 423-436.
- Sarkar, J., & Sarkar, S. (2018). Bank ownership, board characteristics and performance: Evidence from commercial banks in India. *International Journal of Financial Studies*, 6(1), 17.

- Siddique, A., Khan, M. A., & Khan, Z. (2022). The effect of credit risk management and bank-specific factors on the financial performance of the South Asian commercial banks. *Asian Journal of Accounting Research*, 7(2), 182-194.
- Syafrizal, A., Ilham, R. N., & Muchtar, D. (2023). Effect Of Capital Adequacy Ratio, Non Performing Financing, Financing To Deposit Ratio, Operating Expenses And Operational Income On Profitability At PT. Bank Aceh Syariah. *Journal of Accounting Research, Utility Finance and Digital Assets*, 1(4), 312-322.
- Us, V. (2018). The determinants of nonperforming loans before and after the crisis: Challenges and policy implications for Turkish banks. *Emerging Markets Finance and Trade*, 54(7), 1608-1622.
- Wallgren, F.-M., & Andersson, P. (2018). Board gender diversity and firm financial performance: a study of 100 companies listed on Nasdaq Stockholm. In.
- Yulianti, E., Aliamin, A., & Ibrahim, R. (2018). The effect of capital adequacy and bank size on non-performing loans in Indonesian public banks. *Journal of Accounting Research, Organization and Economics*, 1(2), 205-214.
- Zahoor, N., Lew, Y. K., Arslan, A., Christofi, M., & Tarba, S. Y. (2023). International corporate social responsibility and post-entry performance of developing market INVs: The moderating role of corporate governance mechanisms. *Journal of International Management*, 29(4), 101036.

